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Student-mediated knowledge exchange: reviewing the literature on an unjustly neglected form of interaction between higher education and business

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Introduction

Research on the knowledge exchange between universities and their faculty and staff and non-academic organizations, above all private businesses, is plentiful. However, the bulk of the academic work has been on two institutionalised types of knowledge exchange, knowledge commercialization (via patenting, licensing, spin-off formation) and academic engagement (via research and consulting). Other knowledge exchange mechanisms are not institutionalised, more heterogeneous, in part difficult to measure and it has been suggested that “there is scant evidence in the literature on how to deal with them or the real necessity to institutionalize their management” (Geuna & Muscio, 2009, p. 96).

Still, surveys have frequently obtained the result that these non-institutionalised mechanisms of knowledge exchange which involve students, such as joint theses with companies, employing graduates, participation in university education and training activities, are as common as the institutionalised mechanisms: in Austria (Schartinger, Schibany, & Gassler, 2001), the UK (D’Este & Patel, 2007; Hughes & Kitson, 2012), Norway (Kyvik & Olsen, 2007, cited in Thune, 2009), the Netherlands (Bekkers & Bodas Freitas, 2008), or Switzerland (Barjak & Heimsch, 2020). The rising interest in cooperative and project-based teaching formats in higher education – at least in Europe (European Commission, 2017) – creates further opportunities for joint work of faculty, students, and firms.

Neglecting conceptually and empirically a large, important and possibly growing part of the knowledge exchange between universities and companies is not really satisfactory and creates risks. Decision-makers in universities and policy makers in the fields of higher education and innovation might put a too strong focus on mechanisms related to knowledge commercialization and academic engagement, limit incentives and support to these mechanisms, and develop dysfunctional policies which actually reduce the amount of knowledge exchanged (Arundel & Es-Sadki, 2021; Hayter, Rasmussen, & Rooksby, 2020; Rossi & Rosli, 2015). The strong focus on knowledge commercialization might also create the

impression that universities with few patents, licences, and spin-offs do not transfer knowledge and technologies to society (Rossi & Rosli, 2015; Sánchez-Barrioluengo, 2014), underrepresenting the scope of knowledge exchange activities in teaching-oriented universities (Hewitt-Dundas, 2012; Kitagawa, Sánchez Barrioluengo, & Uyarra, 2016; Rossi, 2018). This would negatively affect the image and reputation of these universities and limit their abilities to contribute to economic development, e.g., because of a reduction of funds, partners, staff, and students.

This paper conducts a literature review on a set of mechanisms that it subsumes under the construct of student-mediated knowledge exchange with a focus on three questions:

1. How can student-mediated knowledge exchange be distinguished from other types of knowledge exchange?
2. What types of student-mediated knowledge exchange have been described in the literature?
3. What are the benefits of student-mediated knowledge exchange for companies, students, and universities?

It is concerned with a clarification and discussion of this construct and differentiation from related constructs in the field of knowledge exchange/transfer and university-industry collaboration. “Contrasting, specifying, and (re)structuring existing theoretical constructs” is described by Post et al. (2020, p. 361) as one of seven possible contributions of review articles to theory-building and operationalisation. The paper first distinguishes student-mediated knowledge exchange from knowledge commercialization and academic engagement. Then it suggests four types of student-mediated knowledge exchange and presents costs and benefits on two types of student-mediated knowledge exchange which are under the control of universities. It ends with a few short conclusions.

Student-mediated knowledge exchange as a third type of knowledge exchange

Most work on university-industry knowledge exchange has focused either on knowledge commercialization or academic engagement. Table 1 gives an overview of both types, but length restrictions of this contribution do not permit a detailed discussion. However, the literature on both types is abundant, for instance, on knowledge commercialization (Geuna & Muscio, 2009; Gores & Link, 2021; Hayter, Nelson, Zayed, & O’Connor, 2018; Kirchberger & Pohl, 2016; Mowery & Sampat, 2005) and academic engagement (Perkmann et al., 2013, 2015, 2021).

Much less has been written on student-mediated knowledge exchange or related concepts such as educational collaboration (Kunttu, 2017) or teaching-based knowledge sharing (Barjak & Heimsch, 2020). Student-mediated knowledge exchange is understood in this contribution as any type of interaction between a university and a company or other organization in which knowledge is exchanged and which involves students and/or student work as significant carriers of knowledge.¹ The role of students in higher education institutions has been debated controversially for some time. Different roles have been suggested, for instance, expressed by means of the metaphors of students as apprentices, consumers, clients or knowledge co-producers (Calma & Dickson-Deane, 2020; McCulloch, 2009; Tight, 2013). These metaphors differ with regard to students' expectations and own contributions to learning success, but none

¹ For conceptual clarity we avoid the concept of “student engagement”, as this has been used commonly to “refer to how *involved* or *interested* students appear to be in their learning and how *connected* they are to their classes, their institutions, and each other.” (Axelson & Flick, 2010, p. 38).

questions the fundamental positive effect of studying on knowledge gain and diffusion. Moreover, students can enter student-mediated knowledge exchange in different phases of their education. They may be early career academics doing industry-related coursework and projects, finish their education and start their professional careers with the most recent academic subject knowledge and skills, or refresh their knowledge on the side and part-time in addition to continuing their professional obligations. So, their involvements in both, the university and the company, are on continua from very little to very much which will influence the success of student-mediated knowledge exchange: The greater the integration into the company, the easier it will be to meet the company's requirements and vice versa (Roolaht, 2015), but the lower the involvement in higher education, the less knowledge will be acquired.

Student-mediated knowledge exchange differs in many regards from academic engagement and commercialization (Table 1). The motivational set is different: raising students' employability and contributing to the third mission of the university are key for student-mediated knowledge exchange, while research-related motivations are largely absent (Orazbayeva et al., 2020). The decision to take up such collaborative work involving students may be taken at all levels: by the individual professor, research group, institute, department, school or entire organization. The higher up the decision is made the more likely student-mediated knowledge exchange is part of a strategic plan (Borrell-Damian et al., 2010). Whenever student-mediated knowledge exchange includes the movement of students between the university and the company, even if only temporarily as in student mobility and lifelong learning, it facilitates the transmission of tacit knowledge to companies (Thune, 2009).

Table 1. Types of interactions between academia and private companies

	Knowledge commercialization	Academic engagement	Student-mediated knowledge exchange
Knowledge carrier	Patent, artefact	Faculty	Students
Typical forms	Academic spin-offs, licensing of academic inventions	Collaborative and contract research, consulting	Joint theses, lifelong learning, student mobility, student start-ups, employing graduates
Benefit for the non-academic partner	Access to use rights for a (patented) academic invention	Research results, proof-of-concepts, problem solutions, knowledge, ideas, etc.	Access to tacit knowledge, academic networks, low-threshold (and partly low-cost) cooperation
Economic value	Direct, monetarised, e.g., through license fees, options and similar	Direct, monetarised, e.g., through research and consulting fees	Indirect, only partially monetarised, e.g., through course fees, wages
Incentives for the academic partner	Financial compensation for academic inventions, use of research in practice	Access to problems, knowledge, technology for research, research funding	Employability of students, contribution to 3rd mission
Responsible structures inside the university	Technology transfer offices	Research offices, industry liaison offices	Education departments/programmes, lifelong learning programmes, career centres, entrepreneurship centres

Student-mediated knowledge exchange should be distinguished from other, teaching-related forms of interaction between companies and higher education institutions such as cooperation in curriculum design (Borah, Malik, & Massini, 2019, 2021; Plewa, Galán-Muros, & Davey, 2015), sponsored professorships, or guest lectures of managers and professionals in universities. Through the latter companies can influence the content of education, raise the chances that students acquire the skills that companies need, and strengthen their brand. However, the interaction between the company and the student is less intensive than in student-mediated knowledge exchange. Direct access to students is often not given and the possibilities to identify qualified students are lower. In addition, whereas student-mediated knowledge exchange can be framed as one dimension of the impact of science on practice via its education function (Aguinis, et al., 2019) this does not apply to these other teaching-related interactions.

Forms of student-mediated knowledge exchange

Different forms of such student-mediated knowledge exchange have been described. They often relate to universities' teaching activities and involve different types of student groups. We differentiate these transfer mechanisms by two criteria: a) locus of control and b) type of knowledge that is transferred.

The locus of control distinguishes mechanisms over which the university and its faculty have some authority from mechanisms over which primarily the student has control. The former are for instance university decisions to offer education programs, to request certain activities from students (e.g., internships) or to permit or even endorse collaboration with non-academic entities. Universities can decide strategically to engage in such transfer mechanisms and deepen their relationships with the private sector. This is less possible with regard to mechanisms where the students themselves make the decision, e. g., where to work after graduating or whether to start a new company. As the publishing of student work illustrates, the boundaries are not always clear-cut and it might well be that universities make the publication of student work mandatory or at least push it, e. g., theses. However, as authors students have the final word on the content of any publication they write. Therefore, I consider this mechanism as being largely under student control as well.

Second, mechanisms that contain tacit knowledge which is literally contained in students' minds are distinguished from mechanisms that contain predominantly codified knowledge, especially the results of student work. Tacit knowledge can be know-how, knowledge that is too new and not enough understood or too expensive to be fully codified and therefore taught via "learning-by-doing" in the lab (Cowan, David, & Foray, 2000). Most importantly, it needs the mobility of students for being transferred. The properties of knowledge, including its tacitness and systemic character, have been found to influence the importance of channels of knowledge transfer for university and industry researchers (Bekkers & Bodas Freitas, 2008).

Table 2 gives an overview of the different mechanisms which can be subsumed under each of the four types of student-mediated exchange. The space restrictions of this paper do not permit a detailed discussion. For each type a number of costs and benefits have been discussed. For instance, it has been found that students engaged in cooperative graduate work with firms might lose (part of) their autonomy and be expected to prioritise consulting work over PhD research, causing delays and even jeopardising the success of a partnership (Bienkowska & Klofsten, 2012; Zalewska-Kurek & Harms, 2020), and that scientific creativity and out-of-the box thinking might be reduced (Borrell-Damian, 2009). Moreover, an industrial focus in the PhD might affect negatively the academic career possibilities (Lee & Miozzo, 2015). However,

commonly more benefits than downsides have been found. Table 3 differentiates these for university-controlled exchanges and differentiates between the three involved groups of participants, universities and their faculty, firms, and students.

Table 2. Forms of student-mediated knowledge exchange

Type of knowledge exchanged	Controlled by the university	Controlled by the student
Codified knowledge, included in student work results (e.g., theses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint supervision and/or financing of doctoral theses • Joint supervision and/or financing of master's and bachelor's theses • Student projects • Student consulting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of student work
Tacit knowledge, embodied in students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifelong learning • Temporary student mobility • Cooperative education program 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employment of graduates • Student entrepreneurship

Table 3. Benefits of university-controlled student-mediated knowledge exchange

University	Firm	Student/graduate
University-controlled exchange of explicit knowledge		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional firm-funded infrastructure • Higher competencies and understanding of practical problems in firms, integration of practical input into the research • Extending networks and strengthening positions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New ideas and knowledge, broader competencies • Access to talented future employees • Increased legitimacy of processes, products in the industrial application • Building trust between HEI and industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased motivation • Additional learnings • Higher academic achievement and skills • Improved job opportunities
University-controlled exchange of tacit knowledge		
<i>Life-long learning (LLL)</i>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generating additional revenue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquisition of cutting-edge scientific knowledge and skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquisition of cutting-edge scientific knowledge and skills
<i>Temporary student mobility</i>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback on the fit/mismatches of program contents and corporate needs • Higher employability of graduates boosts HEI image 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure to students' ideas and knowledge • Access to talented future employees • Higher success of recruitments as candidates are known • More visibility and reputation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure to different (research) environments • Acquisition of practical knowledge and competencies • Improved employability

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appreciation of employing HEI graduates 	
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Sources: (Assbring & Nuur, 2017; Berbegal-Mirabent, Gil-Doménech, & Ribeiro-Soriano, 2020; Borah et al., 2019; Borrell-Damian, 2009; Callanan & Benzing, 2004; Chen & Yang, 2019; Franco, Silva, & Rodrigues, 2019; Guo, et al., 2020; Gustavsson, Nuur, & Söderlind, 2016; Hasanefendic, Heitor, & Horta, 2016; Kunttu, 2017; Kunttu, Huttu, & Neuvo, 2018; Lam, 2007; Mangematin, 2000; Marhl & Pausits, 2013; Molas-Gallart et al., 2002; Piterou & Birch, 2014; Salminen-Karlsson & Wallgren, 2008; Thune, 2009; Thune & Børing, 2015; Weible, 2009)

Conclusions

Student-mediated knowledge exchange can be clearly differentiated from other related concepts. Even though several benefits for universities, firms, and students have been identified, it remains a neglected type of knowledge exchange.

A key barrier to giving it a higher prominence in the knowledge exchange strategies of universities and in higher education and innovation policy-making is the lack of data and measures. Studies on measuring knowledge exchange and third mission activities of HEI have commonly suggested measures on student-mediated knowledge exchange (European Commission Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture et al., 2017; Marhl & Pausits, 2013; Molas-Gallart et al., 2002; de la Torre, Casani, & Perez-Esparrells, 2021), but they have not yet implemented, let alone been integrated into national surveys of higher education institutions, knowledge transfer offices, or graduates. Even recent initiatives stress that knowledge transfer metrics should include teaching-mediated transfers but exclude them from their suggested set of core indicators (Campbell et al., 2020). This is above all due to the difficulty of collecting reliable data which rarely exists at the level of the organization, but only in sub-units or at the level of individual faculty. Further pilot studies and surveys are needed to better integrate student-mediated transfers into knowledge exchange and third mission activities.

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